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ON THE TECHNIQUES OF CHINESE - KAZAKH LEXICAL TRANSLATION

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Abstract

In the context of contemporary globalization and integration, cross-cultural and cross-linguistic communication has become increasingly common. This creates broad prospects for the development of translation while simultaneously assigning it a more significant role and responsibility. Translation courses are important components of language education aimed at improving students' translation competence. To achieve the objectives of this course, instructors should not only clearly define its nature and requirements but also approach teaching from the perspectives of translation theory and practice. By applying various teaching methods, teachers can help students combine theoretical knowledge with practical skills and thereby improve the quality of Chinese-Kazakh translation. As Chinese-Kazakh translation is taught within the framework of less commonly taught languages, instructors should pay particular attention to innovation in course design, supplement and improve existing teaching materials, and incorporate newly emerging vocabulary from contemporary political and economic discourse into the teaching process. This approach helps increase students' interest in Chinese-Kazakh translation courses.

Keywords: translation, teaching, culture, lexical meaning, methods

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Translation is a linguistic activity that has accompanied the entire historical development of human society. Speakers of different languages rely on translation to open channels of communication and dialogue, thereby achieving mutual understanding. In today's environment of globalization and integration, cross-cultural and cross-linguistic communication has become increasingly common. This provides broad prospects for the development of translation while simultaneously assigning it a more significant mission. In translation teaching, the course "Translation" is a specialized subject with strong theoretical and practical components. It is also an important course aimed at improving students' translation competence, with the primary goal of continuously enhancing students' bilingual knowledge and practical translation skills. "The process of translation, which involves the transformation between two languages, is a complex cognitive process that moves from the surface level to the rhetorical level and further to the deep level. During the process of transformation, translators must compare lexical, grammatical, rhetorical, logical, and cultural background elements in order to select appropriate means of expression at different levels. The translation process can be divided into two interrelated stages: comprehension and expression. Comprehension is the prerequisite for expression, while expression represents a further deepening of comprehension" [1, p. 8]. In recent years, in order to effectively teach the course Translation Theory and Practice to undergraduate students, the author has not only become thoroughly familiar with the syllabus and recommended teaching materials but has also extensively consulted other relevant literature. Based on this work, the author has summarized several experiences and reflections during the teaching process, which are shared here with colleagues and specialists for academic discussion.

II. Requirements for the Professional Competence of Translators

1. Solid Bilingual Competence

Translation involves the transformation between two languages; therefore, strong bilingual competence is the fundamental prerequisite for becoming a translator. Translators must be able to accurately and thoroughly understand the content of the source text and faithfully express it in the target language in a fluent and natural manner, including clear expression, correct grammar, and appropriate lexical choice. Interpreters must translate the content of the source text objectively and faithfully so as to provide listeners with the most accurate information for judgment and understanding.

A translator is also, in a sense, an author; however, the translator's writing must be based on the text of the original author. Therefore, translators need strong writing skills in the target language. Different types of texts place different demands on the translator's writing abilities. Among the many types of translation, literary translation requires the highest level of writing proficiency. Literary translation may require professional or even exceptional writing talent. Outstanding literary translators are often accomplished writers themselves. For example, renowned translators such as Qian Zhongshu and Yu Guangzhong, who translated foreign literature, were also distinguished writers in their own right.

2. Cultural Competence

Since language is a carrier of culture, translation is not merely a transformation at the linguistic level but also communication at the cultural level. It serves as a bridge for cultural exchange among people of different ethnic groups, nations, contexts, and life backgrounds. Therefore, translators must possess rich cultural competence, including knowledge of the source language and culture, a deep understanding of the target language and culture, and the ability to recognize and handle differences between the source and target

cultures. Translators need to accurately capture and thoroughly understand the cultural information embedded in the source language and reproduce it in the target language, conveying the core message while minimizing the loss of information.

3. Reasonable Translation Strategies

A translator may not necessarily study translation theory in depth, but it is impossible to work effectively without having one's own translation strategies. Even if translators do not consciously reflect on translation principles, their personal experience, knowledge, character, and aesthetic views gradually shape their unique translation strategies. Through continuous translation practice, translators should master the principles, methods, and techniques of translation.

4. Broad Knowledge Base

A translator should be a versatile intellectual possessing knowledge in many different fields. This includes history, geography, customs and traditions, literature and art, religion, and other areas. Moreover, translators should continuously expand their knowledge base, since it is impossible to predict what subjects or disciplines the translation materials may involve. Professor Shi Zhentian, who studies Chinese-Uyghur translation, pointed out: "Teachers who teach translation courses should guide students to carefully compare the two languages and understand both their similarities and differences. In the process of translating Chinese into Uyghur, it is relatively easy to grasp and explain the common features of the two languages, but explaining their differences is not easy. Therefore, when teaching translation courses, teachers should actively guide students to compare Chinese and Uyghur, and the translation techniques dealing with differences between the two languages must become the key and difficult focus of teaching" [2, p. 64].

5. Professional Ethics

Translators must possess strong professional ethics. This includes maintaining the confidentiality of clients' commercial secrets and personal privacy, strictly complying with contractual terms, and completing translation tasks according to the client's requirements. At the same time, translators should respect the author's intention and the linguistic style of the original text, avoid arbitrary changes to the original wording, and respect both the linguistic and cultural background of the source text.

6. Keeping Pace with the Times and Continuous Learning

Translators need to continuously learn in order to improve their knowledge and skills. This includes learning new languages, gaining deeper understanding of cultural backgrounds, and mastering new technological translation tools and skills. Only through constant learning can translators keep up with the development of the times and improve their professional competence.

II. Flexible Use of Various Teaching Methods

The aspects mentioned above represent only several basic requirements for teachers of translation courses. However, to teach translation effectively, instructors should flexibly apply various teaching methods.

(1) Guiding Students to Improve Their Translation Skills Through Practice. Students should engage in extensive practice, including translation exercises, translation assignments, and translation evaluation tasks. Teachers should also design more practical and targeted teaching activities so that students' translation competence can improve more rapidly. To achieve effective teaching outcomes in translation courses, the following strategies and methods may be applied. First, teachers should select excellent translation examples and conduct comparative analyses between Chinese and Kazakh texts. Through the analysis of multiple translation cases, students can identify optimal translation solutions, summarize translation experience, and improve their translation competence. In particular, students should be guided to understand the cultural connotations and national sentiments embedded in lexical items. Regarding the cultural connotations of lexical meaning in translation, Cong Yaping and other scholars who study Chinese-Russian

translation theory and teaching point out: "Culture-specific words refer to lexical items deeply embedded in the Russian language that carry cultural background information related to Russian history, geography, customs, and national psychology. If such words are translated into Chinese literally, it may not cause difficulties for those familiar with Russian culture. However, for readers who do not know Russian or are unfamiliar with Russian cultural realities, such translations may be confusing or even lead to misunderstanding" [1, p. 172]. Therefore, translators need to possess strong cultural competence, including knowledge of the source language and culture, a deep understanding of the target language and culture, and the ability to identify and deal with differences between the two cultures. Second, students should be encouraged to translate independently. Whether in class or outside the classroom, students will encounter various linguistic problems during translation. Teachers should encourage independent translation and comparative analysis of different translation results, which greatly helps to develop students' translation competence. For example, at the entrance of a factory workshop there is a slogan: **安全生产重于泰山** The Kazakh translation is: **Өндіріс қауыпсыздығы бәрінен маңызды (Production safety is more important than anything else)**. If students interpret the phrase **“重于泰山”** literally as "more precious than Mount Tai," this would be incorrect. Teachers should guide students to understand the metaphorical meaning of this expression before translating it and distinguish between the meanings "precious" and "grave/important," thereby improving the accuracy of translation. The idiom **“重于泰山, 轻于鸿毛”** originates from Sima Qian's work *报任安书* of the Western Han Dynasty: "人固有一死, 或重于泰山, 或轻于鸿毛". It contrasts Mount Tai with a feather to illustrate the difference in the value of life. **“重于泰山”** indicates great significance, while **“轻于鸿毛”** describes a death lacking value. English translation: **weightier than Mount Tai, to lay down one's life for a noble cause is worthwhile.**

Around 110 BCE, Sima Qian began compiling historical records, inheriting the unfinished scholarly mission of his father Sima Tan. Sima Tan had passed away with regret because he had been unable to participate in Emperor Wu of the Han Dynasty's **Fengshan ceremony on Mount Tai**, and before his death he entrusted Sima Qian with completing the historical work. In 99 BCE, Sima Qian was implicated in the **Li Ling incident** and was sentenced to castration. Enduring humiliation, he continued his writing and eventually completed **Records of the Grand Historian (Shiji)** around 91 BCE. In his letter to **Ren An**, he expressed the idea of evaluating the value of life through the significance of death and proposed the famous statement: **"Death may be weightier than Mount Tai or lighter than a feather."** The Cultural Significance of Mount Tai. The **Taishan District** is a jurisdiction of **Tai'an City**, located in the central part of the city and bordering **Mount Tai** to the north. Since ancient times, Mount Tai has symbolized stability and peace. For this reason, people naturally associated Mount Tai with the stability of the state and society. One of the earliest expressions of this idea appeared in the **Letter to Emperor Wu** written by **Liu An**, the Prince of Huainan during the Han Dynasty: **“天下之安, 犹泰山而四维之也。”** This means that **the stability of the country is like Mount Tai secured firmly by strong ropes (immovable and unshakable)**. In Kazakh, this idiom can be translated as: **Адам түбінде бір өледі. Кейбіреудің өлімі Тайшан тауынан да қадірлі, кейбіреудің өлімі қауырсыннан да қадірсіз.** (Every person will eventually die. Some people's death is more honorable than Mount Tai,

while others' death is lighter than a feather).

(2) **Organizing Translation Competitions.** In order to increase students' interest in translation courses, organizing translation competitions can be an effective approach. Through such competitions, teachers can evaluate students' translation works, identify strengths and weaknesses, and stimulate students' motivation to study translation more actively.

(3) **Encouraging Students to Publish Excellent Translation Works.** Teachers can organize students to translate texts of different genres. After the students submit their translations, the teacher reviews and revises them, selects the best works, and recommends them to publishing institutions for possible publication. This can encourage students to continue improving their translation skills.

(4) **Guiding and Encouraging Students to Write Translation Research Papers.** In the teaching process, theory should be combined with practice. Teachers should guide students to summarize their translation experience, record and analyze it, and encourage them to write short academic papers on translation. For example, students can analyze translation standards, translation techniques, translation theories, translation methods, and translation criticism. By systematically collecting and summarizing these small research results, valuable academic outcomes can gradually be achieved.

(5) **Effective Use of Multimedia Teaching Tools.** The development of modern multimedia technologies makes it possible for teachers to use audio, images, and video materials in classroom teaching. Teachers should skillfully apply multimedia tools to present vivid examples and expand the background information related to translation. This approach not only increases students' interest but also helps them master translation knowledge more effectively. For example, when explaining translation techniques, teachers may display the following sentence on the screen. As the scholar **Serik Mustafa**, who studies translation methodology, pointed out: "Although polysemous words may have several meanings, they are usually not confused in actual language practice because the linguistic context allows one meaning to emerge while excluding the others" [3, p. 36]. This can be illustrated in the following sentence: **“有的人喜欢吹毛求疵, 抓住工作中的一点缺点就大做文章。”** In this sentence, the expression **“做文章”** in Chinese has two meanings: 1. to write an essay; to engage in intellectual or artistic exploration (write an essay); 2. metaphorically, to make an issue out of something, to comment excessively on it, or to use it as a pretext for criticism or ulterior motives. Therefore, the specific meaning of this word can only be determined according to the context. Consequently, if teachers supplement their explanations with relevant examples or related materials, the effectiveness of translation teaching may be significantly improved. According to the context, the Kazakh translation of the expression **“做文章”** in this sentence is: **Жоқ нәрсені дабырайтып көрсету, түймедей істі түйедей қылу.** (To exaggerate something insignificant; to make a mountain out of a molehill).

(6) **Incorporating New Phenomena and New Achievements into Teaching.** Today's world is characterized by rapid development and transformation, with new concepts and new vocabulary constantly emerging. Teachers should introduce new phenomena and recent developments from both domestic and international contexts during lectures and attempt to translate them. Many of these new terms are closely related to political and economic life. Translating such terms allows students to obtain new information from the field of translation, broaden their horizons, and stimulate their interest in extracurricular reading. For example,

the recently popular internet term “躺平” (*lying flat*) describes the attitude of some young people toward work and life. It refers to a mindset of indifference toward situations that cannot be changed or controlled, characterized by a lack of ambition, minimal effort, and spending whatever one earns - similar to the mentality of “living only for the present moment.” Some social observers worry that if this attitude spreads widely, it may even develop into a social or national concern. As a result, this term has entered contemporary political discourse in Chinese. In *Kazakh*, this concept can be translated as: *масыл болу, масылдық* (to be dependent on others, dependency).

III. Teaching Considerations

In teaching Chinese - Kazakh translation courses, several future directions can be considered.

First: Course Innovation. Some of the currently used teaching materials contain redundant sections and areas that require supplementation. Therefore, it is necessary for teachers to adapt the existing materials and develop practical new textbooks for translation teaching. These textbooks should clearly explain the basic concepts, methods, and techniques of translation. Translation examples should be carefully selected so that example words and sentences are typical and modern, and the translated texts should cover a variety of genres and topics. Although several published textbooks on Chinese-Kazakh translation are currently in use and some are considered authoritative, no textbook is perfect. Therefore, teachers should adjust the course content according to teaching objectives, students' needs, and practical conditions, supplementing new materials in order to achieve the intended teaching goals.

Second: Focusing on Improving Students' Translation Competence. The essence of translation is the **equivalent transformation between two linguistic forms**, and this equivalence must be based on the principles of “**faithfulness, expressiveness, and elegance.**” To achieve standardized translation, every stage of classroom teaching should serve the purpose of improving translation ability. Students should understand that translation is also a process of **re-creation**, and teachers should encourage them to apply creative thinking in translation practice.

Third: Developing Students' Practical Translation Skills. It is important to develop students' practical translation activities and their ability to analyze linguistic difficulties and solve problems independently. Teachers should emphasize not only grammatical knowledge in written language and written translation but also **oral translation skills**, improving students' language expression abilities in both written and spoken forms. As translation theorist **Cong Yaping** notes: “Translation, as the transformation between two languages, is a complex cognitive process that moves from the surface level to the rhetorical level and then to deeper levels. During this process, translators compare vocabulary, grammar, rhetoric, logical thinking, and cultural background to select appropriate means of expression. The translation process consists of two interwoven stages: comprehension and expression. Comprehension is the prerequisite for expression, while expression further deepens comprehension” [1, p. 8].

Without sufficient linguistic competence, difficulties may arise in understanding and expressing the ideas of the source text. Chinese cognitive linguist **Wang Yin** also noted in his research: “Human cognition is based on the understanding of the self and space, developing gradually from the near to the far, from the concrete to the abstract, and from bodily and spatial experience to other semantic

domains. In human perception and experience, the body and space play a primary role; they form the basis for many other concepts (including abstract ones) and serve as the starting point of primitive thinking and the fundamental source of abstraction and creativity” [4, p. 50]. For example, when discussing the concept of the “**Chinese Dream**”, it represents a political concept or governing philosophy. After translation into Kazakh or Russian, it becomes: “**Қытай арманы.**” (“**Chinese Dream.**”). However, the Kazakh word **арман** (dream / aspiration) does not mean **dream during sleep** (*мұс*) but rather **dream, aspiration, or ideal**. In Chinese, there is also a distinction between **梦** (dream) and **梦想** (dream/aspiration). The word **dream** may refer either to a dream during sleep or to an unrealistic illusion, while **aspiration** expresses hope and expectations for the future. Therefore, in the expression “**Chinese Dream**”, the word “**dream**” clearly does not refer to a psychological phenomenon such as “**I had a dream**” (Kazakh: **Мен мұс көрдім**). Chinese President **Xi Jinping** defined the **Chinese Dream** as “**the realization of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation,**” emphasizing that this dream “**will certainly be realized.**”

Fourth: Increasing the Interest of Translation Courses. A lively and engaging classroom atmosphere allows students to learn in an enjoyable way and increases their motivation. Language contains many vivid and interesting expressions. If teachers select typical translation examples, the lesson becomes both interesting and effective. Researchers **Tang Kesheng** and **Hu Xiaoshen** noted when discussing the determination of word meaning in translation: “Structural meaning is not entirely reliable in translation. As is well known, translation differs from reading. In reading, guessing the meaning of unfamiliar words from context is an acceptable reading strategy. However, translation requires converting one language into another and therefore demands accuracy” [5, p. 38]. For example, the expression “**中国梦**” translated into Kazakh as “**Қытай арманы**” (“**Chinese Dream**”). If a translator uses the dictionary meaning of the word “**dream**” without considering the context, the meaning may not be conveyed correctly. By analyzing such vivid examples in class, teachers can reduce students' boredom and distraction and achieve the expected teaching objectives.

Conclusion, in order to achieve the teaching objectives of Chinese-Kazakh translation courses, teachers must carefully prepare in advance and clearly understand the nature and requirements of translation teaching. It is necessary to select attractive topics and translation examples that engage students and improve classroom effectiveness. Teachers should also carefully summarize teaching methods and continuously innovate their teaching approaches, thereby achieving the expected teaching outcomes.

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